

Assessment of Dose Rates from Water Activation and Contamination in Tokamak Cooling Circuits

Nicholas Terranova ^{1*}, Andrea Colangeli¹, Michele Lungaroni¹, Fabio Moro¹, Simone Noce¹

¹ENEA, Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development, Nuclear Department, Via Enrico Fermi 45, Frascati, Rome, Italy.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20804006

ABSTRACT

In the safety demonstration of fusion facilities, the occupational dose estimation covers an important role. Knowing precisely the expected dose absorbed by the working personnel involved in maintenance activities is extremely important to pursue the ALARA (As Low As Reasonably Achievable) principle, and to verify if the safety objectives are actually addressed. To perform reliable occupational radiation exposure assessments aimed at providing information to the designers, not only maintenance duration and frequencies are needed, but also precise dose rate maps in the several possible positions where hands-on interventions are expected to be performed.

In fusion technology, the determination of dose rate maps around the most important components constituting the Primary Heat Transport System (PHTS) assumes particular importance for the determination of the occupational dose, shielding design, remote handling conception, and maintenance plan scheduling. In this work we propose a possible methodology to estimate the dose rate due to water activation and contamination. The main radiological source terms considered are the intrinsic activation of water which yields to the formation of ^{16,17}N, and the Activated Corrosion Products (ACP) which are the main responsible for water and piping contamination in the primary cooling systems. Preliminary results are provided for the primary cooling system of the divertor cassettes and plasma facing components in the European DEMO design.

Keywords: Dose rate, water activation, activated corrosion products, DEMO

1. INTRODUCTION

Maintenance activities in Tokamaks involve many parts of the machine and they may require human hands-on interventions. Radiological source terms deriving from component contamination and direct activation are responsible of intense radiation fields which may affect occupational safety, increasing sensitively the collective dose of the working personnel involved in maintenance operations. The determination of the dose rate maps in the tokamak building rooms is a fundamental step in the safety demonstration, providing important data for Occupational Radiation Exposure (ORE) assessments [1]. In the framework of the EUROfusion Safety and Environment Work Package (WPSAE), a specific methodology has been put in place to estimate dose rate maps around the most significant components constituting the Primary Heat Transport System (PHTS) of the European DEMO. The components outside the bio-shield, even if not directly irradiated by the neutron flux, are susceptible to be contaminated by Activated Corrosion Products (ACP) in form of surface inner oxides, deposits, ions in solutions, and particles in suspension [2].

Uniform corrosion of structural materials in contact with the flowing water leads to the formation of a double layer oxide at the wet interface between the primary coolant and the metal, and to the release of ions in the working fluid. Erosion and agglomeration processes allow the formation of particles in suspension. Under neutron flux, these corrosion products generate ACP, which contaminate the water

*nicholas.terrano@enea.it

and the surfaces of the cooling pipes. In similar cooling systems, such as those used in Pressurized Water Reactors (PWRs), they account for more than 85% of the occupational radiation dose [2].

Furthermore, assuming water as the main cooling fluid as in the Water Cooled Lithium Lead (WCLL) concept of DEMO breeding blanket (BB) [3], or in the Divertor (DIV), intense radiation fields might be produced by direct coolant activation (e.g. through $^{16}\text{O}(n, p)^{16}\text{N}$). Rapid decaying isotopes, such as ^{16}N , might not be relevant for occupational dose determination in preventive scheduled maintenance operations. However, dose rate maps induced by direct water activation are worth to be calculated for component material qualification, room classification, and shielding design purposes.

In the following sections, a specific procedure used to calculate dose rates in the PHTS of EU-DEMO is presented. ACP results have been produced using OSCAR-Fusion V1.4a (Outil de Simulation de la Contamination en Réacteur) [4], a code developed by CEA to perform ACP estimation in closed water cooling systems tailored to fusion application. Water activation data have been provided by UNED, through the means of ACAB Loop [5]. A specific Python interface has been developed to load ACP and water activation specific activities and build ad-hoc gamma sources for MCNP. To perform gamma transport calculations, patched version of MCNP-6.2 capable of sampling surface and volumetric sources in piping geometries has been used. This patch, called pipe-source and provided to ENEA by the UKAEA, allows to sample specific sources in MCNP cylindrical cells which turned to be very useful for this specific purpose.

Preliminary results are provided in the last section of the manuscript concerning the water activation and contamination in the EU-DEMO Divertor PHTS.

2. THE DOSE RATE CALCULATION METHODOLOGY

2.1. Description of the methodology

Defining source terms coming from water activation and contamination might be a cumbersome task. Radiological hazards must be quantified and translated into MCNP sources to perform gamma transport calculations. This exercise was primarily aimed at quantifying dose rates due to ACP and water activation.

A dedicated methodology was developed to collect source terms coming from OSCAR-Fusion and ACAB Loop activation calculations, and to produce specific input files to be used by a patched version of MCNP 6.2 [6]. Figure 1 shows the graphical representation of the methodology applied for ACP calculations. Integral activation reaction rates are firstly calculated to be used in OSCAR-Fusion, as described in [7]. Then OSCAR-Fusion solves mass balance equation for corrosion, deposition, dissolution, precipitation, filter purification, fluid advection, and erosion mechanisms. The Bateman equation for radioactive isotopes is solved to take into account neutron induced activation and decay. These inventories have been then used in a dedicated Python Application Programming Interface (API) to produce pipe_source files and spectra for MCNP 6.2. In the following sections the methodologies used to quantify those source terms are briefly described. The final subsection is devoted to the production of the corresponding gamma sources for MCNP. Gamma transport calculations are then performed with MCNP 6.2 to obtain the dose rate maps at different operation shut-downs or cooling times.

2.2. ACP Calculations

The piping metal in contact with the flowing water undergoes uniform corrosion which produces a double oxide layer. It has been experimentally observed that, for stainless steel, the outer oxide layer is made of tetrahedral crystals, richer in iron, and more detachable and irregular than the inner oxide layer, which is denser and richer in chromite. The corrosion products under neutron flux are activated and the different phenomena at play induces contamination all over the circuit. Surface activities are given by the activated deposits and inner oxide. Volumetric sources dispersed in the cooling water are given by ions in solution and particle in suspension.

Figure 1. Dose rate calculation scheme for water contamination due to ACP.

In fusion technology, ACP in primary cooling circuits are calculated with dedicated codes which simulate transport of contaminants inside the loops. Some examples are PACTITER [8], TRACT [9], CATE [10], and OSCAR-Fusion [4] among the others. In this work the version 1.4a of OSCAR-Fusion has been used to estimate ACP inventories in DEMO PHTS. OSCAR-Fusion, a code developed by CEA in France, allows to calculate ACP inventories in their different forms all over the cooling circuit, once it has been discretized in regions with assigned geometry, water chemistry, and thermal-hydraulics properties. It derives from OSCAR, the fission-specific version the code, validated using experimental integral measurements acquired from the French PWR fleet.

Figure 2. EU-DEMO Primary Heat Transport Systems.

Figure 3. Divertor PHTS model implemented in OSCAR-Fusion. The 48 sectors have been lumped in 4 branches. In-vessel components have been specified for the divertor cassettes (CAS) and plasma facing units (PFU).

Figure 2 shows a CAD drawing of the EU-DEMO PHTS, with details specified for the breeding blanket and divertor balance of plant components. The design refers to a 2021 scheme, where the divertor cassettes and plasma facing units are cooled separately, with heat exchangers and main cooling pumps located at Level 3 of the Tokamak building. The divertor PHTS has been modelled in OSCAR-Fusion as two separated inputs for the cassette body (CAS) and the plasma facing unit (PFU) cooling, respectively. The 48 sectors have been lumped in 4 branches, with specific in-vessel modelling for the two sub-system (see Figure 3). It ought to be emphasized, that at the time of present calculations, an updated MCNP model for the EU-DEMO PHTS was not available. As matter of examples of the results obtainable with the methodology presented in this manuscript, an obsolete MCNP model of the divertor PHTS components hosted in Level 1 was inevitably used, as the only currently available. Specific activities have been reported and preserved in the MCNP input, gamma sources have been generated using the actual cell surfaces of the photon transport model.

In the frame of the Safety and Environments Work Package of EUROfusion, OSCAR-Fusion calculations have been extensively carried out for all the main PHTS in EU-DEMO. Further details can be found in [11, 7].

2.3. Water Activation

Water activation data were not directly produced in the frame of the present work, but they were courteously provided by UNED using ACAB Loop [5]. ACAB Loop allows to take into account the pulsed irradiation of a flowing media, and it has been used to calculate activation in pure water. Volumetric specific activities have been provided for several PHTS of EU-DEMO and they have been used in this work to generate gamma sources for dose rate calculations. Even if water activation does not have particular impact on the occupational dose due to the fast decaying of the most significant radionuclide i.e. ^{16}N , knowing the dose due to water activation may provide important indications to the designers of the several systems to predict the dose levels during operation in the Tokamak building.

Volumetric activity concentration in water were provided at shut-down, after the first operational phase of EU-DEMO, corresponding to a damage in the structural materials of the vacuum vessel of 20 dpa. To take into account that water in the components outside the bio-shield and constituting the PHTS had the time to decay just before the shutdown, decaying factors estimated using the time of travelling in the cooling circuits have been calculated. Such decay factors have been estimated as a decay after an average time of travelling of the cooling water along the circuit as follows:

$$D_c = e^{-\lambda \sum_{i=0}^{c-1} \tau_i} \cdot \frac{1}{\tau_c} \int_0^{\tau_c} e^{-\lambda t} dt \quad (1)$$

where $e^{-\lambda \sum_{i=0}^{c-1} \tau_i}$ takes into account the decay along the series of upstream components, $\tau_c = \frac{L_c}{\langle v_c \rangle}$ is the time required to the water to flow along the component c , L_c is the component length and $\langle v_c \rangle$ the average fluid speed. It is worth mentioning that the flow regime in DIV-PHTS is fully turbulent, so this linear behaviour would fit better a water volume flowing in laminar regime, without any mixing. Future evaluations of the water activation will include CFD corrections, and a more rigorous treatment of the radioactive decay along the cooling circuit.

2.4. Gamma Sources Production and Transport Calculations

Once ACP and water activation inventories are available sources must be built for gamma transport calculations. A Python API has been developed to convert OSCAR-fusion and water activation data into input files used by a MCNP 6.2 patched version (`pipe_source`) which samples surface and volume sources. The Python API uses Actigamma [12], a specific FISPACT module that allows to convert the activities in gamma intensities at specific energies. Such gamma lines have been used to define spectra used by `pipe_source`. With this patch, cylindrical bodies corresponding to the PHTS piping cells in the MCNP model have been tagged with a specific gamma intensities. Each cell is then initiated to emit source photons in the simulation according to the spectra obtained from Actigamma.

Due to the mismatch between the region discretization assumed in OSCAR-Fusion, and the cell implementation in MCNP, specific activities values have been preserved. To derive total activities in the water volumes or the wet surfaces to be used in the `pipe_source` routine sampling, specific activities coming from OSCAR-Fusion and ACAB Loop have been preserved. Surfaces and volumes of the MCNP cells definition in the input deck have been multiplied by the specific activity values provided by OSCAR-Fusion and ACAB-Loop to calculate absolute activities and then gamma intensities.

To provide results in terms of biological dose rate, fluence-to-effective-dose conversion factors have been taken from ICRP-74 [13]. The only external exposure has been considered.

3. DOSE RATE RESULTS

3.1. Dose Rates from Water Activation

To test the capabilities of the methodology discussed in this work, preliminary dose rate maps have been calculated for water activation at shut-down and after arbitrary cooling times. Dose rate maps

have been evaluated for the DIV-PFU components only. The operation scenario at 20 dpa of DEMO has been simulated by UNED with ACAB Loop to produce volumetric specific activities [5]. The gamma

(a) Dose rate map due to water activation in DIV-PFU-PHTS at shut down. (b) Dose rate map due to water activation in DIV-PFU-PHTS at 300s after shut down.

Figure 4. Dose rate maps due to water activation in DIV-PFU-PHTS.

emission and transport have been simulated using MCNP 6.2, patched with the pipe_source routine provided by UKAEA. The major contribution to the gamma dose is due to ^{16}N , which is characterized by a half-life of 7.13 s. It is well known that water activation does not pose any concern in terms of occupational dose. The typical cooling times preceding scheduled preventive maintenances are generally sufficient for the complete decay of ^{16}N .

Assessing dose rate maps due to water activation is however important due to the impact on the overall safety demonstration of the system. They affect component qualification and shielding, they impact on room classification during operations, and they characterize the room conditions in case corrective maintenances are required. After shut-down, water activation dose rate are extremely high, of the order of $10^{10} \frac{\mu\text{Sv}}{\text{h}}$ which reduces to $5 \cdot 10^3 \frac{\mu\text{Sv}}{\text{h}}$ after only 300 s (see Figures 4a and 4b), showing the fast decaying of pure water under EU-DEMO neutron flux after shut-down.

3.2. Dose Rates from Activated Corrosion Products

ACP are relevant source terms which might contribute significantly to the occupational dose. They determine the majority of the dose rate levels around the components constituting the PHTS, and their assessment is of fundamental importance in the safety demonstration process. Figures 5a and 5b show dose rate maps due to activated deposits and inner oxide in the DIV-PFU-PHTS components, only. At the first ex-vessel maintenance, after around 70 days of operation, the dose rate levels around the heat exchanger have already reached few decades of $\frac{\mu\text{Sv}}{\text{h}}$. At the end of the first operational phase of EU-DEMO, at 20 dpa, thousands of $\frac{\mu\text{Sv}}{\text{h}}$ are given by the only surface oxides in the PFU components, giving great concerns on the dose the working personnel is susceptible to absorb.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this manuscript a methodology to assess dose rate maps due to water activation and contamination is proposed for primary cooling systems in Tokamaks. Dose rates from ACP and pure water activation are calculated using a patched version of MCNP 6.2, considering the external exposure due to gamma-emitting radioactive isotopes. The contamination of the cooling circuits is assessed with OSCAR-Fusion

(a) Dose rate map due to surface ACP (deposits and inner oxide) in DIV-PFU-PHTS at the beginning of the first ex-vessel maintenance. (b) Dose rate map due to surface ACP (deposits and inner oxide) in DIV-PFU-PHTS at the end of the first operation scenario at 20 dpa of EU-DEMO.

Figure 5. Dose rate maps due to surface ACP in DIV-PFU-PHTS.

v1.4, a code developed by CEA to assess ACP in water cooling loops. Water activation data have been provided in this work by UNED, using ACAB Loop. A Python API has been developed to generate input files and spectra for the pipe_source patch to perform gamma transport calculations with MCNP 6.2. To test the capabilities of this methodology the DIV-PFU-PHTS of EU-DEMO has been selected. The preliminary results obtained showed the possibility to exploit successfully this methodology in dose rate calculations around PHTS in Tokamaks. Preliminary results on the EU-DEMO PHTS dose rates for the contamination and activation of the PFU components are provided, showing significant dose rate levels which have to be seriously considered in the safety demonstration of the machine. Future work will be devoted to the production of dose rate maps obtained from the whole ACP contamination of the PHTS in the tokamak building, including source terms inside the breeding blanket, the divertor, the vacuum vessel, and the limiters cooling systems of EU-DEMO.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors wish to acknowledge M. Garcia from UNED for providing water activation data for the main PHTS in EU-DEMO, and T. Barry and T. Eade from UKAEA for providing the pipe source patch.

This work has been carried out within the framework of the EUROfusion Consortium, funded by the European Union via the Euratom Research and Training Programme (Grant Agreement No. 101052200 - EUROfusion). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be held responsible for them.

REFERENCES

- [1] G. Caruso, S. Ciattaglia, B. Colling, L. D. Pace, D. Dongiovanni, M. D'Onorio, M. Garcia, X. Jin, J. Johnston, D. Leichtle, T. Pinna, M. Porfiri, W. Raskob, N. Taylor, N. Terranova, and R. Vale. "DEMO – The main achievements of the Pre – Concept phase of the safety and environmental work package and the development of the GSSR." *Fusion Engineering and Design*, volume 176, p. 113025 (2022).

- [2] C. Cherpin and F. Dacquait. "Modeling particle deposition in the primary circuit of pressurized water reactors for the OSCAR code." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 199**, p. 110364 (2024).
- [3] P. Arena, A. Del Nevo, J. Aktaa, G. Bongiovì, L. Bühler, I. Catanzaro, S. Cesaroni, G. Caruso, B. Chelhi, C. Ciurluini, A. Collaku, F. Colliva, C. Garnier, F. Giannetti, P. Haghdoust, V. Imbriani, F. Lucca, P. Maccari, L. Maqueda, L. Melchiorri, C. Mistrangelo, G. Mongiardini, F. Moro, T. Moulignier, R. Mozzillo, S. Noce, I. Pagani, J. Pontier, T. Pomella Lobo, M. Principato, P. Ruiz, L. Savoldi, S. Siriano, A. Tassone, F. Urgorri, F. Viganò, and Yañez. "Design of the WCLL BB in view of the conceptual design phase." *Fusion Engineering and Design*, **volume 218**, p. 115205 (2025).
- [4] F. Dacquait, J. B. Génin, and L. Brissonneau. "Modelling of the contamination transfer in nuclear reactors: the OSCAR code applications to SFR and ITER." In *1st IAEA workshop on challenges for coolants in fast neutron spectrum systems* (2017).
- [5] M. García, J. P. Catalán, and J. Sanz. "ACABLoop simulation tool: Improving the activation prediction of flowing PbLi alloy in support of DEMO fusion reactor design." *Fusion Engineering and Design*, **volume 204**, p. 114485 (2024).
- [6] C. J. Werner, J. S. Bull, C. J. Solomon, F. B. Brown, G. W. McKinney, M. E. Rising, D. A. Dixon, R. L. Martz, H. G. Hughes, L. J. Cox, et al. "MCNP Version 6.2 Release Notes." Technical report, Los Alamos National Lab. (LANL), Los Alamos, NM (United States) (2018).
- [7] N. Terranova, P. Chiovaro, F. Dacquait, I. Moscato, and E. Vallone. "Activated corrosion product contamination assessments of DEMO WCLL breeding blanket primary heat transport system." *Fusion Engineering and Design*, **volume 199**, p. 114132 (2024).
- [8] L. Di Pace, D. Tarabelli, and D. You. "Development of the PACTITER code and its application to the assessment of the ITER divertor cooling loop corrosion products." *Fusion technology*, **volume 34**(3P2), pp. 733–737 (1998).
- [9] P. Karditsas and A. Caloutsis. "Corrosion and activation in fusion cooling loops—TRACT." *Fusion Engineering and Design*, **volume 82**(15), pp. 2729–2733 (2007). Proceedings of the 24th Symposium on Fusion Technology.
- [10] L. Li, J. Zhang, W. Song, Y. Fu, X. Xu, and Y. Chen. "CATE: A code for activated corrosion products evaluation of water-cooled fusion reactor." *Fusion Engineering and Design*, **volume 100**, pp. 340–344 (2015).
- [11] N. Terranova, S. Breidokaité, G. M. Contessa, L. Di Pace, C. Gasparrini, T. Kaliatka, and G. Mariano. "Activated Corrosion Products Evaluations for Occupational Dose Mitigation in Nuclear Fusion Facilities." *Environments*, **volume 9**(7) (2022).
- [12] URL <https://github.com/fispact/actigamma>.
- [13] International Commission on Radiological Protection. *Conversion Coefficients for use in Radiological Protection against External Radiation*, volume ICRP publication 74. International Commission on Radiological Protection (1996).